

STRATEGIES FOR MANAGING CLASSROOM BEHAVIOR
IN SPECIAL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article gives more information how to explore practical techniques for assessing behaviors, setting clear expectations, designing an engaging classroom, and refining interventions to successfully manage special education behaviors.

Key words: classroom behavior, managing skill, strategies, engaging classroom

Special education classrooms can present unique behavioral challenges. Students with disabilities often exhibit problems like noncompliance, disruptiveness, aggression, or self-injury. Without proper management, these behaviors can severely impact learning. This section provides an overview of common special education behavioral issues and the importance of implementing effective strategies. Students in special education frequently demonstrate challenging behaviors related to their disabilities. For example:

- Noncompliance: Refusing to follow directions, passivity, or failure to respond.
- Disruptiveness: Yelling, tantrums, constant noisemaking that interrupts instruction.
- Aggression: Hitting, kicking, throwing objects, verbal threats, etc.
- Self-injury: Head banging, skin picking, hand biting, or other self-harming actions.

It's critical to understand these behaviors often communicate an underlying need. Determining the function through assessment can inform strategies.

When inappropriate behaviors occur, they can significantly disturb learning, lower class wide self-esteem, and reduce instructional time. For example, aggressive

episodes may trigger peers' flight-or-fight response, making concentration difficult. Or students may internalize beliefs that misbehavior reflects poorly on them. Unmanaged behaviors also have long-term impacts like poor academic outcomes or negative school sentiments. Implementing consistent strategies is essential.

Effective classroom management aims to:

- Provide needed structure through schedules, clear expectations, etc.
- Meet unique student needs by adapting the environment, accommodating disabilities.
- Actively teach and reinforce positive replacement behaviors.
- Foster student independence and self-regulation skills.

With consistency and effort, special education teachers can create safe, productive environments where all students succeed.

Dealing with disruptive behavior in a special education classroom can be challenging. Here are some effective strategies:

*Set clear expectations and rules. At the start of the year, collaboratively create classroom rules with students. Visual rules can help students remember. Praise students when they follow them.

*Build relationships. Get to know each student, their triggers, interests, etc. A strong bond makes redirecting behavior easier.

*Use positive reinforcement. Compliment students when they demonstrate good behavior. Consider using a reward system. This encourages continuity.

*Remain calm and patient. Students with behavioral disorders often act out when escalated. Keep a neutral, understanding tone to de-escalate situations.

*Modifications and accommodations. Adjust lessons and activities to suit disabilities causing acting out. Accommodations relieve stressors.

*Work with support staff. Collaborate with other staff to create Behavior Intervention Plans for recurrent issues. Consistency across staff is key.

Managing behavior in a special education classroom can be challenging, even for experienced teachers. Seeking out professional development opportunities and collaborating with other staff can provide the skills and support needed to create a positive learning environment. Open communication between teachers and parents is key for addressing behavior issues consistently at home and at school. Strategies include:

- Set up regular check-ins through phone calls, emails, or meetings to provide updates on progress.
- Create a system for parents to provide quick daily or weekly feedback on their child's behavior and mood at home.
- Involve parents in developing customized behavior plans tailored to their child. Explain techniques being used in the classroom so they can be reinforced properly at home.
- Use a communication log to track interventions attempted and the child's response so all parties remain coordinated.

Establishing strong home-school relationships demonstrates a united front to students and enables complementary behavior management strategies.

Successfully supporting students with special needs demands teamwork between all stakeholders - teachers, support staff, administrators, parents, and students themselves. Maintaining open communication and working together establishes an environment where students can thrive. Classroom management is an ongoing process, but with concerted collaboration, we can ensure student growth.

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